

Preparation and Catalytic Activity of Polymeric *meso*-Tetra (4,4'-Biphenylene-bisulpho)phenylporphyrin and its Complexes

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The construction of artificial P-450 catalysts has recently attracted much attention¹, and a synthetic metalloporphyrin has been used to catalysed the transfer of one oxygen atom to the hydrocarbon substrates from a variety of active single-oxygen donors, such as iodosobenzene, hypochlorite salts, percarboxylic acids and hydroperoxides etc.². Polymer-supported metalloporphyrins have been developed mainly to investigate the reversible binding of dioxygen³. They have been used in the surface modification of electrodes⁴ and in photo-induced electron-transfer⁵, and as models for peroxidase, catalase⁶ and cytochrome P-450⁷. Here we report the preparation of the polymeric *meso*-tetra(4,4'-biphenylene-bisulpho)phenylporphyrin (PH₂TBPBSPP) and the corresponding transition metal (Cu, Zn) complexes (PMTBPBSPP) (Fig. 1), and their use in the oxidation of cyclohexene by molecular oxygen.

Fig. 1. PMTBPBSPP.

Results and Discussion

The electronic spectra of the polymeric ligand and its complexes are as follows : λ_{max} (PH₂TBPBSPP) 422.1 (Soret band), 524.2, 558.7, 599.0, 658.2 nm (Q band); (PCuTBPBSPP) 415.7 (Soret), 538.2; (PZnTBPBSPP) 426.2 (Soret), 564.4, 599.4 nm; ν_{max} (KBr) the absorption of S=O stretching vibration are near 1 375 and 1 180 cm^{-1} (S=O). The weak absorption of ν_{NH} (3 314 cm^{-1}) and δ_{NH} (966 cm^{-1}) for the ligand disappear in the complexes. The strong absorption near 1 000 cm^{-1} , appears to be a characteristic absorption for all metalloporphyrin⁸. The results of thermal analysis of PH₂TBPBSPP and PCuTBPBSPP are very different (Figs. 2 and 3). PCuTBPBSPP burns at 414.1° as if oxygen molecules are

Fig. 2. T-TG-DA curve of PH₂TBPBSPP.

Fig. 3. T-TG-DA curve of PCuTBPBSPP.

easily adsorbed in the core of CuTBPBSPP. Zinc complexes appear similar to the curve of T-TG-DA of the ligand. The polymeric ligand and its complexes have also been characterised by scanning electron microscope and fluorescence spectra.

Oxidation of cyclohexene catalysed by PCuTBPBSPP in the presence of molecular oxygen afforded 1,2-cyclohexanediol (1) and 1,2-cyclohexanedione (2) without any solvent and the selectivity to total ketone (2) and alcohol (1) is more than 77%. The results are given in Table 1.

The influence of base and acid to the catalytic activity and the product selectivity were investigated. When pyridine was added to the reaction mixture of cyclohexene and PCuTBPBSPP as catalyst, the conversion of cyclohexene increased from 13.2 to 22.5% and the product selectivity of 1 and 2 increased from 77.9 to 81.3%. But the conversion was decreased by adding HOAc. Reaction rate was reduced dramatically by adding hexamethylene tetramine [(CH₂)₆N₄].

No activity of PZnTBPBSPP or the monomeric copper-porphyrin complex (CuTHPP) was found in the oxidation of cyclohexene under the same condition. It has also been found that ethylbenzene could be oxidised by dioxygen

TABLE 1—OXIDATION OF CYCLOHEXENE CATALYSED BY PMTBPBSPP*

Catalyst	Additive	Conversion mol%	Products selectivity (%) to 1 and 2
PCuTBPBSPP	-	13.2	77.9
	Py (0.5 mmol)	22.5	81.3
	(CH ₂) ₆ N ₄ (0.007 mmol)	5.9	76.7
	HOAc (1.5 mmol)	11.7	77.1
PZnTBPBSPP	-	trace	-

* Reaction condition : Cat. = 4.31×10^{-3} mmol, cyclohexene = 20 mmol; 9 h at 60°; 1 atm O₂

in the presence of the cupric complex.

Experimental

Pyrrole and propionic acid were freshly distilled before use. Chloroform was dried and distilled. All other reagents used were of accepted grades of purity. Electronic spectra were measured on a Hitachi U-3400 spectrophotometer and IR spectra (KBr) on a Alpha-centauri FT-IR spectrophotometer. TG-DTA were obtained with a Shimadzu DT-40 instrument. Elemental analysis was performed on a Carbo-Erba 1106 autoanalyser.

Meso-Tetra (p-hydroxyphenyl)porphyrin (H₂THPP) : A mixture of *para*-hydroxybenzaldehyde (0.1 mol) and propionic acid (250 ml) was stirred and heated. A propionic acid solution (50 ml) of pyrrole (2 mol dm⁻³) was slowly added to it at 110–120°. The reaction mixture was refluxed and stirred for 30 min and then was concentrated to 200 ml. After cooling to ~75°, EtOH (200 ml) was added and then cooled overnight at -15°. H₂THPP (blue amorphous powder) was filtered off and washed with cold C₂H₅OH/CH₃COOH (1 : 1, v/v) for three times, (16%) (Found : C, 70.30; H, 5.03; N, 7.19. C₄₄H₃₀N₄O₄·4H₂O calcd. for : C, 70.40; H, 5.06; N, 7.46%); λ_{\max} (DMF) 418.0 (Soret band), 516.8, 554.9, 594.0 and 650.6 nm.

Polymeric meso-tetra-(4,4'-biphenylene-bisulpho)-phenylporphyrin (PH₂TBPBSPP) : To H₂THPP (0.2 g) dissolved in a solution (10 ml) of NaOH (1.25 mol dm⁻³), the phase transfer catalyst (30 mg) was added, and then stirred for 20 min. To the solution, were added dropwise a solution (5 ml) of 4,4'-biphenylenedisulphonyl chloride (0.25 g) in dry chloroform with vigorous stirring. The resulting

polymeric film was washed thrice separately by water, EtOH and chloroform, and dried (0.2 g, 80%), (Found : C, 65.32; H, 3.79; N, 4.26. C₆₈H₄₂N₄O₁₂S₄ calcd. for : C, 66.13; H, 3.40; N, 4.54%).

Complexation of PH₂TBPBSPP with M(OAc)₂·nH₂O, (Cu(OAc)₂·H₂O, Zn(OAc)₂·2H₂O) was performed in the mixture of H₂O-C₂H₅OH (1 : 1, v/v). The molar ratio of PH₂TBPBSPP to M(OAc)₂·nH₂O was 1 : 10. The pH was adjusted to 4–5 by dilute HOAc. The reaction mixture was heated under refluxed for 6 h with stirring. Products were washed several times with H₂O and C₂H₅OH. Yields of 80% or better of PMTBPBSPP were obtained after drying.

The oxidation of cyclohexene was carried out in a glass reactor. The reaction products were analysed using Shimadzu QP-1000A GC/MS system and GL-16A gas chromatograph with a 5 m × 3 mm OV-17 column.

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